

Receiver-independent GNSS Smart Antenna for Interference Mitigation

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Abstract—The presence of unintentional or intentional Radio Frequency Interference (RFI) signals in the Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) frequency bands is by far one of the main vulnerabilities of every GNSS receiver. This known threat can cause severe positioning performance degradation and even a complete service unavailability. Complementary to time and frequency-domain mitigation techniques, it is well known that antenna-array based receivers can benefit from spatial domain processing. By exploiting spatial diversity, an array-based smart antenna can selectively attenuate the RFIs Direction of Arrival (DOA) and provide high gain towards the legitimate GNSS signals. In this work, we propose a receiver-independent GNSS smart antenna architecture that implements a real-time automatic and autonomous null-steering spatial filtering for GNSS bands. The platform uses Commercial Off The Shelf (COTS) components including a multichannel receiver front-end, a System on Chip (SoC) hybrid FPGA/CPU digital signal processor, and an up-converter to shift the spatially filtered GNSS signal back to its carrier frequency. In this way, the proposed smart antenna can be connected to any conventional single-antenna GNSS receiver. The paper includes both the theory of operation, the implementation details, and the prototype performance in a real-life open field scenario.

Index Terms—GNSS, Antenna Array, Smart Antenna, Jamming, Interference mitigation, Navigation.

I. INTRODUCTION

Radio-frequency (RF) interferences are known to be a major threat to the proper operation of any Global Navigation Satellite Systems (GNSS) receiver [1]. Any non-legitimate RF signal transmitted in the GNSS frequency band, either unintentionally or on purpose, can jeopardize, or even block, the capacity of the receiver to provide Position, Velocity and Time (PVT) fixes. A possible scenario of intentional interference consists of a set of powerful RF signals transmitted with the aim to overwhelm the spectrum being used by the system, thus denying service to all affected user receivers. This is known as *jamming*, and it can be considered a relatively easy-to-deploy Denial of Service (DoS) attack.

The presence of interferences can saturate the analog-to-digital conversion in the receiver chain, so the baseband engine is unable to acquire or track GNSS signals. In the case of interferences which are not continuous in time (e.g., a pulsed interference) or extremely narrowband, they can be mitigated with digital signal processing techniques. In the case of out-of-band interferences, they can be blocked with physical RF filters. But in the case of continuous, wideband, in-band interferences, a conventional GNSS receiver remains unprotected.

The solution proposed in this paper consists of a smart antenna (also known as Controlled Reception Pattern Antenna or CRPA) that is able to filter out interferences based on their spatial signature, hence acting as an adaptive spatial filter that mitigates those unwanted signals and delivers a *cleaned* RF signal to any conventional (single-antenna) GNSS receiver. The solution has been deployed in a full-featured prototype using commercial-off-the-shelf (COTS) components and System-on-Chip (SoC) technology, and then tested in realistic scenarios using commercial GNSS receivers, hence demonstrating the feasibility and effectiveness of this approach.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows: Section II describes the signal model for an antenna array, Section III describes the implemented spacial filter algorithm, Section IV provides details of the implementation, Section V reports the testing campaign and results, and finally Section VI draws some conclusions.

II. ARRAY SIGNAL MODEL

A complete GNSS array signal model can be found in [2]. Without loss of generality, in this work we used a simplified N -element antenna array signal model which contains only the contribution of a single GNSS satellite plus a set of uncorrelated interferences or jamming signals and the thermal noise. The notation is as follows: lowercase italics for

scalar variables, either deterministic or stochastic, both real or complex; uppercase italics for constants; lowercase bold for vector variables, column-wise defined; uppercase bold for matrix variables; $(\cdot)^\top$, $(\cdot)^*$, and $(\cdot)^H$ stand for the transpose, conjugate, and conjugate transpose (Hermitian) operators, respectively; and $\mathbb{E}\{\cdot\}$ is the expected value operator. More notation will be defined throughout the paper as needed. At each antenna, the receiving baseband signal can be modeled as:

$$x(t) = as(t - \tau)e^{j2\pi ft} + \sum_{\ell=1}^{M_I} i_\ell(t) + n(t), \quad (1)$$

where a is the amplitude, τ is the delay, f is the Doppler shift for the received LOS satellite signal, $i_\ell(t)$, $\ell = 1, \dots, M_I$ are uncorrelated interferences, and $n(t)$ is additive white Gaussian noise. Each antenna receives a different replica of those signals, with a different phase depending on the array geometry and the direction of arrival (DOA). This can be expressed by a vector signal model, where each row corresponds to one antenna:

$$\mathbf{x}(t) = \mathbf{h}b(t) + \mathbf{H}_I \mathbf{i}(t) + \mathbf{n}(t), \quad (2)$$

where:

- $\mathbf{x}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the observed signal vector (snapshot),
- $\mathbf{h} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ is the spatial signature matrix related to array geometry and DOA of the satellite signal,
- $b = as(t - \tau)e^{j2\pi ft}$ is the delayed and Doppler-shifted satellite signal envelope, as received in the phase center of the antenna array,
- $\mathbf{H}_I \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M_I}$ is the spatial signature matrix related to array geometry and DOAs of the interferences,
- $\mathbf{i}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{M_I \times 1}$ are the uncorrelated M_I interferences, as received in the phase center of the antenna array, and
- $\mathbf{n}(t) \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times 1}$ represents additive white Gaussian noise received at each antenna.

The spatial signature matrix $\mathbf{H} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$, where N is the number of antennas and M is the number of modeled wanted or unwanted signals, can be expressed as a function of the scenario geometry and the electrical characteristics of the antenna array:

$$\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{C}\mathbf{G}, \quad (3)$$

where matrix $\mathbf{C} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times N}$ models RF channels' gain and phase unalignments, as well as cross-coupled terms, which can be measured in a calibration process. On the other hand, the matrix $\mathbf{G} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times M}$ depends on the geometry of the array and on the direction of arrival of the M sources or considered scatterers, and it is uniquely defined for a set of sources emitting from different directions. Considering a local coordinate system (for example, an east-north-up or $[e, n, u]$ system with origin in a reference point, usually the phase center of the whole array), the delay between the array antenna elements $\Delta t_{m,n}$, where m refers to a given source and n refers to a given antenna, can be computed as the dot product of the wave vector \mathbf{k}_m (with modulus $\frac{2\pi}{\lambda_m}$, being λ_m the carrier wavelength of signal m and its direction pointing to the signal

source, defined by its azimuth ϕ_m and elevation θ_m) and the position of the antenna center of phase, \mathbf{r}_n . Generalizing this example for M sources and N antennas with arbitrary geometry, the time delay of each source caused in each antenna can be computed and expressed in a matrix form

$$\mathbf{G} = e^{j\pi(\mathbf{K}\mathbf{R})^\top}, \quad (4)$$

where $\mathbf{K} \in \mathbb{R}^{M \times 3}$ is the wavenumber matrix, defined as:

$$\mathbf{K} = \begin{pmatrix} \cos(\phi_1) \cos(\theta_1) & \sin(\phi_1) \cos(\theta_1) & \sin(\theta_1) \\ \vdots & \vdots & \vdots \\ \cos(\phi_M) \cos(\theta_M) & \sin(\phi_M) \cos(\theta_M) & \sin(\theta_M) \end{pmatrix}, \quad (5)$$

having its rows pointing towards the corresponding emitter, being ϕ_i the angle of the source i defined anticlockwise from the e axis on the en plane and θ_i the angle with respect to the en plane. On the other hand,

$$\mathbf{R} = \begin{pmatrix} r_{e_1} & \cdots & r_{e_N} \\ r_{n_1} & \cdots & r_{n_N} \\ r_{u_1} & \cdots & r_{u_N} \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{3 \times N} \quad (6)$$

is the matrix of sensor element positions normalized to units of half wavelengths with respect to the e , n , and u axes.

In this model, the *narrowband array assumption* has been made. This assumption considers that the time required for the signal to propagate along the array is much smaller than the inverse of its bandwidth and, thus, a phase shift can be used to describe the propagation from one antenna to another.

The GNSS signal $s(t)$, whose waveform is known at the receiver, is transmitted using spread-spectrum techniques (see [3] for a description of GNSS civil signals), resulting in a received signal buried in noise. Therefore, a collection of K snapshots (usually spanning one or more spreading codeword periods) are used to take advantage of the despreading gain.

Suppose that K snapshots of the impinging signal are taken with a sampling interval T_s satisfying the Nyquist criterion. Then, the sampled data can be expressed as

$$\mathbf{X}[k] = \mathbf{h}\mathbf{b}[k] + \mathbf{H}_I \mathbf{I}[k] + \mathbf{N}[k], \quad (7)$$

using the following definitions:

- $\mathbf{X}[k] = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{x}(t_{k-K+1}) & \cdots & \mathbf{x}(t_k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$, referred to as the *spatiotemporal data matrix*, where we used $t_k \equiv kT_s$,
- $\mathbf{b}[k] = \begin{pmatrix} b(t_{k-K+1}) & \cdots & b(t_k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{1 \times K}$, known as basis function vector (single satellite signal model),
- $\mathbf{I}[k] = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{i}(t_{k-K+1}) & \cdots & \mathbf{i}(t_k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{M_I \times K}$, known as the interference functions matrix, and
- $\mathbf{N}[k] = \begin{pmatrix} \mathbf{n}(t_{k-K+1}) & \cdots & \mathbf{n}(t_k) \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{C}^{N \times K}$.

III. SPATIAL FILTER ALGORITHM

The goal of the proposed smart antenna design is to provide a generic protection against GNSS interferences and jamming signals compatible with the existing COTS *single antenna* receivers. It implies the following constraints:

- The smart antenna should work without any feedback from the receiver

- The smart antenna should provide a single RF output with similar power levels as a regular active GNSS antenna
- The smart antenna should work in *realtime* with an acceptable signal processing delay (i.e. small enough to not affect or distort the positioning application)

Among the available algorithms candidates present in the literature [2], one of the most effective and simple algorithm is the *blind null-steering*. This type of antenna array is used to sense the presence of interfering signals and adaptively placing reception nulls in the direction of arrival of such signals. Hereafter can be found a brief summary of the algorithm design.

The power minimization design constraint can be written as:

$$\begin{aligned} \arg \min_{\mathbf{w}} \mathbb{E} \left\{ |\mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{X}|^2 \right\} \\ \text{subject to } \mathbf{w}^H \boldsymbol{\delta}_0 = 1, \quad \boldsymbol{\delta}_0 = [1, 0, \dots, 0]^T, \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

which leads to the well-known closed form expression for its optimum weights set:

$$\hat{\mathbf{w}}_{\text{PMIN}} = \frac{\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\text{XX}}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\delta}_0}{\boldsymbol{\delta}_0^T \hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\text{XX}}^{-1} \boldsymbol{\delta}_0}, \quad (9)$$

where $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\text{XX}} = \frac{1}{K} \mathbf{X} \mathbf{X}^H$ is an estimation of the autocorrelation matrix of the received snapshots. This power minimization approach is founded on the fact that GNSS signals are received well below the noise floor (and can be recovered based on their corresponding spreading sequence), and thus they pass through the beamformer seamlessly. On the contrary, any interference or jamming signal with higher power than the thermal noise floor will force the algorithm to automatically attenuate its DOA to keep the minimum signal power at the beamformer output. This architecture can steer up to $N - 1$ nulls by adjusting a set of N control weights, since only one degree of freedom is consumed in constraining the reference element weight to be unity.

IV. IMPLEMENTATION

The proposed CRPA core architecture is shown in Figure 1, where the antenna array delivers a single output that can feed a *conventional* (i.e., single antenna) receiver. From left to right, a multichannel front-end receives N GNSS RF signals¹, down-converts them coherently and digitizes the resulting baseband snapshots. The baseband signal sample stream is feed directly to the SoC FPGA fabric. In the digital domain, the signal processing chain is divided in two groups:

- *Computing intensive operations* processed at the snapshots sampling rate are implemented in the SoC FPGA fabric as custom IP accelerators. This is the case of the autocorrelation matrix estimation $\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\text{XX}}$ and the beamforming operation $y = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x}$, and,
- *complex and high-level operations* such as matrix inversion and matrix multiplication are implemented in a software running on the SoC ARM CPU.

¹In the current implementation the smart antenna is composed of four elements, half-wavelength circular array.

Fig. 1. Null-steering beamformer core diagram.

Fig. 2. Prototype implementation high-level block diagram.

In this way, the implementation reach real-time operations with a 100 Hz null-steering CRPA update. Next sections give further details about the hardware and software implementation.

A. Array elements, RF Front-end and SoC FPGA board

In order to reduce the implementation time, the CRPA was implemented entirely with COTS components and evaluation boards. Figure 2 shows the complete prototype high-level block diagram, from left to right, four dual-band L1/E1 + L5/E5 Tallysman TW1825 [4] antenna patches were arranged in a half-wavelength circular array enclosure. The antenna outputs are feed to bias-T modules in order to power its integrated LNAs. Their RF signal outputs are connected to an Analog Devices' FCOMMS5 evaluation board [5], which integrates two dual-channel RF front-end IC AD9361 [6]. The FCOMMS5 includes all the necessary components (reference signal generator and RF switches) to perform the required carrier phase alignment calibration. The reader is

Fig. 3. Antenna array prototype including array elements, front-end, DSP and user interface display.

referred to [7] for more information about the phase alignment procedure.

The front-end daughter board is connected using a dual FMC LPC connector to a Xilinx ZC706 evaluation kit [8] where all the DSP operations are implemented. The software side uses a customized embedded GNU/Linux system based on PetaLinux Tools v2018.3 [9] to run the high-level operations and the graphical user interface (GUI). Finally, the spatially-filtered baseband signal is sent in real-time to one of the AD9361 Tx channels, tuned also to the selected GNSS frequency². The analog output is exposed to the user as an SMA connector after a convenient attenuation to match the average GNSS signals' power level at the Earth surface.

The prototype is enclosed in a 1U rack mount and uses a compact HDMI touch screen as the main interface, as shown in Figure 3. Among the GUI interface, the CRPA platform offers a Gigabit Ethernet connection which enables the remote operation and the digital stream of baseband samples that allows a direct connection to a software-defined receiver, such as GNSS-SDR [10], [11], or to a sample recorder device.

B. System-on-Chip signal processing

In order to reach real-time operation, the following custom IP cores were created to offload the high speed and computing intensive operations from the CPU software to the FPGA fabric:

- *Statistics estimation IP* implements a configurable autocorrelation matrix estimator ($\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}}$ and a cross-correlation vector estimator ($\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\mathbf{X}\mathbf{d}} = \frac{1}{K} \mathbf{X}\mathbf{d}^H$ for a future implementation of CRPA algorithms that use a reference waveform \mathbf{d}). Figure 4 shows its Xilinx's Vivado configuration window with the design-time configuration parameters. In runtime, it is operated and configured from memory mapped registers.

²The user can select to operate the CRPA in L1/E1 or in L5/E5.

Fig. 4. FPGA custom IP for snapshot statistics estimation ($\hat{\mathbf{R}}_{\mathbf{X}\mathbf{X}}$).

Fig. 5. FPGA custom IP for beamforming operation ($y[k] = \mathbf{w}^H \mathbf{X}[k]$).

- *Beamformer IP* implements the core beamforming operation $y[k] = \mathbf{w}^T \mathbf{x}[k]$. It receives the weights updates from the software side, the snapshots stream from the front-end and performs the multiplication and addition operation to produce the array output signal $y[t]$. Figure 5 shows its Vivado configuration window with the design-time configuration parameters. In runtime, the weight can be updated from a memory mapped register, reaching update rates from 100 to 200 Hz, depending on the CPU load.
- *Power estimator and dynamic bit selector IP* is a helper IP that implements a signal power estimator and a configurable output bit shift that is used to implement a software-defined digital gain control. In practice, it prevents the saturation of the array output accumulator and the Tx front-end DAC, specially during the presence of strong interferences. Figure 6 shows its Vivado configuration window with the design-time configuration parameters. During runtime, the signal power estimation can be read anytime and the output bits shift can be configured in real-time from memory mapped registers.

Fig. 6. FPGA custom IP for signal power estimation and dynamic bits selector.

C. Signal processing delay

As mentioned in previous section, the signal processing delay introduced by the smart antenna should be bounded to not affect the usability of the protected receiver products (*e.g.*, PVT and observables). Depending on the user application, the maximum allowable delay will be less restrictive (*i.e.*, in a terrestrial vehicle receiver) or highly restrictive (*i.e.*, in a high speed airborne receiver).

In order to minimize the digital signal processing delay, the architecture depicted in Figure 1 avoids the use of any buffer queues in the array snapshots signal path. From left to right, $\mathbf{X}[k]$ is a matrix containing the front-end snapshots delivered by the proprietary FPGA driver IP from the front-end manufacturer's IP core [5]. The snapshots feed the *beamformer IP*, which introduces a latency of 6 DSP clock cycles for the pipelined weight multiplication operation and 3 DSP clock cycles for the addition operation. In the implemented prototype, the DSP signal processing clock is set to 100 MHz, and therefore the delay introduced by the DSP beamforming operation is 90 ns. The end-to-end delay, accounting from the instant in which the wavefront impinges the array elements to the instant in which the same signal is regenerated at the analog output connector, is affected by the following path delays:

- Antenna element group delay, including the internal LNA,
- antenna platform to DSP enclosure cable delay,
- Rx front-end group delay (AD9361), including the amplification chain, the direct conversion to baseband operation, and the ADC converter delay,
- delay introduced by the Analog Devices' FPGA front-end driver IP (Rx operation),
- DSP delay, as mentioned above,
- delay introduced by the Analog Devices' FPGA front-end driver IP (Tx operation),
- Tx front-end group delay (AD9361), including the DAC operation, the up-converter and the signal amplification chain, and
- signal output's RF cable to the user receiver.

Further work is planned to characterize the complete signal delay introduced by the proposed CRPA architecture.

Fig. 7. GUI main window running on the SoC ARM processor.

D. Smart antenna GUI control and monitoring application

The CRPA control is centralized in a GUI application written in C++ with Qt5 [12]. Figure 7 shows its main window. It mimics the signal flow, from the antenna array elements to the filtered output transmitter. The most relevant configuration parameters such as the RF input gain and the AGC control are exposed to the user as sliders and checkboxes. The front-end monitoring parameters, such as the reported RSSI, are also shown in real-time.

The center section of the GUI window is devoted to the spatial filtering algorithm selection and configuration. In the prototype, it is possible to select the null-steering algorithm or a *bypass mode* that takes the input of a selected antenna element and bypasses the received signal to the array output. During the null-steering operation, the system estimates the current Jammer-to-Noise Ratio (JNR) based on the difference in dB of the maximum eigenvalue of \mathbf{R}_{XX} (corresponding to the jammer or interference subspace) and the minimum eigenvalue of \mathbf{R}_{XX} (corresponding to the thermal noise subspace, an assumption valid only if the number of interferences/jammers with different DOAs is less than the number of antenna elements minus one). In addition to the CRPA algorithm tab, additional tabs provide the following information:

- *Antenna pattern* tab shows a real-time CRPA radiation pattern diagram and its maximum gain and maximum attenuation,
- *Signal Monitor* tab enables the input and output baseband spectrum monitoring by computing the FFT, end
- *HW* tab performs an auto-diagnostic HW check, triggers the front-end carrier phase alignment procedure, and configures the front-end parameters such as the carrier frequency and the sampling frequency, plus the digital sample stream options using the Gigabit Ethernet link.

V. TESTING CAMPAIGN

The prototype was tested both in a controlled environment with synthetic GNSS signals and in a real-life open-field scenario. The goal was to evaluate the performance and the protection level offered to a conventional single-antenna

Fig. 8. BIANCHA anechoic chamber setup.

receiver. Next sections briefly describe both setups and show the most relevant results.

A. Anechoic chamber tests and results

The controlled tests were conducted in the BIANCHA anechoic chamber (which stands for "BIstatic ANechoic CHAMber"). The chamber has a spherical bistatic positioning system, which consists of two elevated scanning arms and a dual-axis azimuth turntable (Figure 8). Two types of test were performed: static and dynamic.

In the static tests, the scanning arms were hold in several positions with one or with two jamming threats, from the zenith (0°) to the plane of the antenna ($\pm 90^\circ$), with an angular accuracy of 0.05° . On the other hand, the dynamic tests took advantage of the arm rotation capacity at 2 rpm. Both arms travelled on the same radius from the zenith to the antenna ground plane, in opposite directions. A summary of all the test performed is presented in Table I.

	Start angle	End angle	Start angle	End angle
Static	0° (1)	$\pm 90^\circ$ (1)	$0^\circ / 10^\circ$ (2)	$+90^\circ/-90^\circ$ (2)
Dynamic	0	$\pm 90^\circ$	$0^\circ/10^\circ$ (2)	$+90^\circ/-90^\circ$ (2)

TABLE I

ANECHOIC CHAMBER TESTS. IN BRACKETS, THE NUMBER OF JAMMERS FOR THAT SET OF TESTS.

The interference signals were generated as additive white Gaussian noise (AWGN), 4 MHz bandwidth, -40 dBm power with a central frequency of 1575.42 MHz (GPS L1) for the single threat configurations, and an additional pulse at 1575.92 MHz, -40 dBm for the double threat configuration. The emitter antennas were two corrugated horns.

As can be seen in Figure 9, it was possible to distinguish the interference(s) in both scenarios. Furthermore, the antenna provided a null at the angle of arrival of all the incoming interference signals.

Fig. 9. Two nulls in the antenna radiation pattern, as a response to two jammers with azimuth of $+50^\circ$ and -50° , respectively.

Fig. 10. Antenna array elements setup in a car rooftop.

B. Open sky tests and results

In order to test the response of the prototype in a real-life dynamic scenario, the CRPA antenna array was installed in a car rooftop as shown in Figure 10. All tests were conducted in a specifically-allowed area by the Spanish Ministry of Defence. The front-end/DSP rack and the user screen were installed in the back seat of the car. The reference GNSS receiver to be protected by the CRPA was an u-blox M8T receiver [13], connected directly to the array output SMA connector. The prototype was powered by the 12 V provided by the car battery, and the u-blox receiver was powered by the monitor and control USB port connected to a regular laptop, thus completing a setup that allowed for autonomous operation.

The purpose of the laptop was twofold:

- The laptop was connected to the CRPA Gigabit Ethernet bus in order to show the GUI application, configure the array, take GUI screenshots, and record raw samples for further analysis and debugging, and
- to run the u-blox proprietary control and monitoring soft-

Fig. 11. Setup of the field test campaign from the standpoint of the jamming signal emitter.

ware uCenter, configure the u-blox receiver parameters, and take screenshots of its performance.

Regarding the jamming signals, the following equipment was used:

- Rohde and Schwarz Vector Signal Generator (VSG) SMC100A configured to generate a white noise, 8 MHz bandwidth signal, centered at 1575.42 MHz (GPS L1 / Galileo E1 band).
- Custom car-plug FM CW sweep jammer, centered at 1554 MHz, with a bandwidth of 40 MHz.

Both equipments were placed in an elevated location, as shown in Figure 11, emulating a jamming threat that intends to deny the GNSS service to vehicles on the road. The scenario was such that the car moved along the road, whereas the jammer emitter was pointing at the car all the time.

The first jamming signal broadcasted was a wideband Gaussian noise interference with 8 MHz of bandwidth, generated with the Vector Signal Generator, that impinged the array with an estimated JNR of 33 dB. Figure 12 shows a screenshot of the array control software, configured in **bypass mode** and in the background the uCenter software showing very low satellite carrier-to-noise density ratio (C/N_0) readings (≤ 10 dBHz). In this situation, the u-blox receiver was unable to produce a valid position fix, as the array emulates a single-antenna receiver. On the other hand, Figure 13 shows a screenshot of the same scenario, but with the CRPA configured to run the **Null-steering** algorithm. The GUI shows in the foreground the input spectrum where the wideband interference is clearly visible above the noise floor, and the filtered output spectrum

Fig. 12. Commercial receiver's output with a wideband interference impinging the array in bypass mode.

Fig. 13. Commercial receiver's output with a wideband interference impinging the array in null-steering mode.

where the interference is greatly reduced. In the background, the uCenter software shows acceptable C/N_0 readings in the range of 35 – 45 dBHz, thus validating the CRPA protection. Figure 14 shows the antenna radiation pattern with a prominent null zone corresponding with the interference DOA.

The car-plug FM jammer was also tested in the same scenario. Figure 15 shows in the foreground the jammer spectrum as reported by the CRPA GUI and the filtered output.

Fig. 14. Commercial receiver's output with a wideband interference impinging the array in null-steering mode (uncalibrated array radiation pattern plot).

Fig. 15. Commercial receiver's output with an FM interference impinging the array in null-steering mode.

The u-blox receiver (M8 series) reported also acceptable C/N_0 readings in the order of 34 – 46 dBHz, thus validating also the protection against FM jammers. It seemed evident that the receiver implements some countermeasures for FM interferences (a carrier frequency sweep that can be considered a narrowband interference and can be filtered by an adaptive notch filter, see *e.g.*, [14]). However, the position quality was severely degraded without the protection of the array as the interference power increased.

VI. CONCLUSIONS

This paper described a possible countermeasure for radio frequency interferences in the GNSS band. The proposed solution consists of a smart antenna which can directly feed the antenna input of any conventional (that is, single-antenna) receiver, hence providing an extra protection level against unwanted signals without requiring any external input. After briefly describing the signal model and the algorithm in which the smart antenna is based upon, the text delved into the implementation aspects, providing a description of the system architecture and details about the required hardware and software components. The system was deployed in the form of a fully-featured, reasonably compact prototype built with commercial-off-the-shelf components. Its performance was measured in a state-of-the-art anechoic chamber facility, and then tested in an open field campaign conducted in a specifically-allowed test area.

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REFERENCES

- [1] F. Dovis, *GNSS Interference, Threats, and Countermeasures*. New York, NY: Artech House, 2015, ISBN: 9781608078103.
- [2] C. Fernández-Prades, J. Arribas, and P. Closas, "Robust GNSS receivers by array signal processing: Theory and implementation," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 104, no. 6, pp. 1207–1220, Nov. 2016, DOI: 10.1109/JPROC.2016.2532963.
- [3] C. Fernández-Prades, L. Lo Presti, and E. Falletti, "Satellite Radiocalization From GPS to GNSS and Beyond: Novel Technologies and Applications for Civil Mass-Market," *Proc. IEEE*, vol. 99, no. 11, pp. 1882–1904, Nov. 2011, doi:10.1109/JPROC.2011.2158032.
- [4] Tallysman, "Tallysman TW1825 GPS L1/L5 + GLONASS G1 + BeiDou B1 + Galileo E1/E5a + Navic E5 patch antenna," Ottawa, Canada, June 2021, Online: <https://www.tallysman.com/product/tw1825-embedded-dual-band-gnss-antenna/>. Accessed: December 15, 2021.
- [5] Analog Devices Inc., "AD-FMCOMMS5-EBZ Dual AD9361 Evaluation Board Datasheet," Norwood, MA, June 2021, Online: <https://www.analog.com/en/design-center/evaluation-hardware-and-software/evaluation-boards-kits/eval-ad-fmcomms5-ebz.html>. Accessed: December 15, 2021.
- [6] —, "AD9361 RF Agile Transceiver," Norwood, MA, Sept. 2017, Online: <https://www.analog.com/en/products/ad9361.html>. Accessed: December 15, 2021.
- [7] —, "FMCOMMS5 phase synchronization," Norwood, MA, June 2021, Online: <https://wiki.analog.com/resources/eval/user-guides/ad-fmcomms5-ebz/phase-sync>. Accessed: December 15, 2021.
- [8] Xilinx Inc., *Xilinx Zynq-7000 SoC ZC706 Evaluation Kit*, San Jose, CA, June 2021, Online: <https://www.xilinx.com/products/boards-and-kits/ek-z7-zc706-g.html>. Accessed: December 15, 2021.
- [9] —, *PetaLinux Tools Documentation UG1144 (v2018.3)*, San Jose, CA, Dec. 2018, Online: <https://www.xilinx.com/products/design-tools/embedded-software/petalinux-sdk.html>. Accessed: December 15, 2021.
- [10] C. Fernández-Prades *et al.*, "GNSS-SDR: An open source Global Navigation Satellite Systems software-defined receiver," Website available at <https://gnss-sdr.org>, Accessed on: December 15, 2021.
- [11] —, "GNSS-SDR v0.0.15," Aug. 2021, source code available at <https://github.com/gnss-sdr/gnss-sdr>. Accessed on: December 15, 2021. DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.5242839.
- [12] Qt Group, "Qt5 framework," Webpage, source code and documentation downloadable from <https://doc.qt.io/qt.html>. Accessed: December 15, 2021.
- [13] u-blox, "u-blox M8 concurrent GNSS modules datasheet," Thalwil, Switzerland, Feb. 2017, Online: <https://www.u-blox.com/> Accessed: December 15, 2021.
- [14] J. Arribas, P. Closas, and C. Fernández-Prades, "Interference Mitigation in GNSS Receivers by Array Signal Processing: A Software Radio Approach," in *Proc. of the 8th IEEE Sensor Array and Multichannel Signal Processing Workshop*, A Coruña, Spain, June 2014, pp. 121–124, DOI: 10.1109/SAM.2014.6882355.